

Title: Unlocking the power of natural language by machine translation: hot technologies and business benefits

Mohamed Ali SOLA^b

^a

^b *Data Scientist (NLP Specialist) @ R&D, "Omniscien Technologies", Thailand*

Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

With more than 7000 languages spoken across the world, it becomes more and more important to connect people and cultures together.

In The Age of Globalization, being open to interact with cultures is crucial for an organization to create the unbreakable value for their customer around the globe.

This unique selling proposition should go beyond the production part to deeply go to their customers their culture and build that bridge. Here the language should be a winning card.

Machine translation shows a real impact for improving business process in some parts and avoid to be blocked by a language barrier as translate user-generated content and have a clear idea about customer satisfaction and improve customer acquisition strategy.

The major advantages for having a Machine Translation system are saving time and money, ensuring security for confident data and offering multiple pair of languages at once.

Machine Translation have seen a lot of progress in the last years due to technologies progress and it is applied in different applications in Data science such as natural language processing, deep learning and artificial intelligence.

However, sometimes translation case goes wrong like the recent example of Scrambled in translation, when Norway Olympics team orders 15,000 eggs instead of 1500 eggs by mistake at South Korean games.

It becomes clear that using advanced technologies in the right way will significantly increase the quality of the translation and deliver a high quality of a natural language generated by machines.

2. Aim

Machine translation technologies have changed rapidly in recent years, enabling a range of new processing capabilities.

March 21, 2018

Static or periodically trained Machine Translation alone is not enough; a live engine training platform is needed as well as new approaches to teach an engine to translate.

Enhancements that find/manufacture Machine Translation corporate via Machine Learning/AI in conjunction with other NLP tools, should be applied to assist in keeping Machine Translation engines up to date.

Machine Translation that adapts delivers a higher quality translation output and includes rich metadata created via cross language data enrichment.

What is the purpose behind machine translation?

Make translation system able to learn and evolve as language and news evolves in order to substantially and sustainably enhance and maintain translation quality.

3. Material and methods

The what - Output

Modern Custom Machine Translation Systems, specifically systems based upon machine learning based algorithms, require vast amounts of high-quality training data. In addition, in an environment that process rapidly changing content sources such as in academia, intelligence, news and other environments with rapidly evolving language and content, keep systems current and able to adapt to the changing needs rapidly is of utmost importance.

The How - Process

To design and implement a process pipeline that sources, ingests, intelligently matches, aligns and prepares data from a wide range of public sources and in many different formats to create training data on an ongoing basis.

This training data, is then subsequently injected into a training pipeline that provides rapid neural engine enhancements as to enable the system to learn and evolve as language and news evolves in order to substantially and sustainably enhance and maintain translation quality.

4. Results

Reaching a competitive result (better Bleu score comparing to Google and Bing)

Hybrid NMT/SMT: Integrating NMT (Neural Machine Translation) and SMT (Statistical Machine Translation) together into a single translation delivers even higher quality output.

Deep NMT: July 2017 – The latest advance in NMT, allows for more complex processing of input signals and notably higher quality translations.

For entertainment industry, Machine Translation with the recent technologies, enhancement and improvement, enabled this industry field to reduce translation time (for movies and series, etc.)

From couple of days to couple of hours and for multiple pairs of languages.

5. Conclusions

Translation based domain can impressively improve the quality of translation.

Automated Rapid Adaptation of Machine Translation scope is a necessity.

As Content and topics change, and always will, Machine Translation engines and NLP tools can keep up with change using rapid adaptation approaches that learn continuously in near-real time.

With The Demand of different languages changes based on real world events, the infrastructure must be able to scale capacity up and down automatically in order to meet the throughput demand cost effectively

6. Keywords

Machine Translation, Machine Learning, Natural Language Processing, Deep Learning, Language models, Quality of Translation

Author biography

Mohamed Ali SOLA is a Data science enthusiast with experience in various aspects of NLP and machine translation.

Dali had an engineer degree from at TEK-UP university in Tunisia and studied two Master degree in Business Intelligence and Innovation management from an international program called “ Dicamp ” at 3 universities and school of engineer in Tunisia.

His core interest lies in “NLP”, ”Deep learning”, “Machine Learning”, ”Machine Translation” and "IA".

In 2017 he get rewarded from ATB BANK for his solution "smart-HR", a human resource solution that deal with talents hiring issue, using NLP and IA .

He attended several conferences and hackathons as a speaker and he was a machine-learning trainer in engineering schools in Tunisia.